

Lab-on-a-Scalpel: Medical tool incorporating a disposable fully 3D-printed electrochemical cell promoting drop-volume chemical analysis in the operating theater

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Abstract: Surgical operations are intricate and invasive procedures that require continuous monitoring of the patient's biochemical profile. Point-of-care testing would allow healthcare professionals to identify abnormalities and make the necessary interventions to minimize the risk of complications and ensure patient safety. To this end, we report the development of a disposable and compact fully 3D-printed electrochemical cell incorporated into a medical scalpel (Lab-on-a-Scalpel) aiming to promote on-site (electro)chemical analysis in the operating theater. This multifunctional device minimizes the number of instruments needed during surgery and can be fabricated on-demand using a desktop-size 3D printer at a very low cost. The performance of the Lab-on-a-Scalpel sensing device was evaluated over various electrochemical techniques (Cyclic Voltammetry, Amperometry, Differential Pulse Voltammetry) and different setups (stirring, drop-volume analysis, polarization potentials, etc) for the determination of epinephrine. Results showed attractive analytical figures-of-merit, with the limit of detection (LOD) reaching 0.13 μM , and high accuracy in recovery studies conducted on artificial blood samples. Our findings suggest that Lab-on-a-Scalpel is a valuable tool that enables near-patient diagnostics with a minimum sample volume and holds promise to become an essential tool for robotic-assisted surgery.

Introduction

Surgical operations are critical and complex procedures due to their invasive nature that disrupts the physiological functions of the human body. The inherent risks associated with such operations include bleeding, infection, damage to surrounding tissues or organs, and adverse effects to medication or implants. These issues can compromise the post-surgical recovery, biological functions or even the survival of the patients. Therefore, the continuous monitoring of their conditions is imperative in order to identify abnormalities and risks and make early interventions.^[1-3] Beyond the typical vital signs that need to be tracked during surgery (heart rate, blood pressure, respiratory rate, temperature, oxygen level, blood loss, fluid levels, etc.), the abrupt concentration change of biomarkers, metabolites and stress hormones in the biological fluids of a patient is also indicative of surgical complications and abnormalities.^[4-6]

The requirements of instantaneous and on-site chemical analysis in surgical operation rooms cannot be met by the current methods of chemical analysis (such as chromatographic^[7] and spectroscopic techniques^[8]) due to high instrumentation and operation costs, lack of portability, and the demand of qualified personnel to obtain reliable results. In recent years, mobile testing and rapid diagnostics through Point-of-Care (PoC) technologies have attracted notable interest from the scientific community and medical professionals. A PoC-compatible method relies on affordable, portable, and user-friendly devices that enable reliable and rapid diagnostics outside a laboratory setting.^[9,10] Employing PoC methods in the operating theater during a surgical procedure provides real-time patient diagnostics by eliminating the need for paperwork. The long waiting times behind test ordering and receiving of lab reports can be significantly decreased. This way the clinician can coordinate care by making faster and more informed decisions and engage in improved treatment plans that lead to an overall better patient post-surgical recovery.^[11,12]

Electrochemical sensors possess multiple benefits (portability, affordability, easy miniaturization, high sensitivity, etc.) that render them attractive options for on-site chemical analysis and, thus, PoC diagnostic devices.^[13] The integration of carbon allotropes (graphene, carbon black, and more) in thermoplastic materials unlocked the use of 3D printing technology for the fabrication of low cost and sustainable electrochemical sensors on-demand. This approach enables the fabrication of advanced electrochemical sensing devices without any design constraints.^[14] The desktop size and affordability of a 3D printer in combination with the fast and easy fabrication process render fused deposition modeling (FDM) an ideal method for electrochemical sensor production.^[15]

So far, several studies have utilized FDM 3D printing for the fabrication of electrodes,^[15] cells,^[16-18] and devices^[19,20] for analytical purposes. Even though most of these sensors offer promising analytical features, there are some considerations that need to be addressed so as to be suitable for near patient monitoring in surgical operations: i) to minimize the demand for large sample volumes, which are limited and scarce during a surgical procedure, ii) to provide a compact sensing platform that will integrate all the necessary components without the need of assembling and iii) to be cost-effective for single-use to avoid

cross-contamination in a sterile environment such as the operating room.

Herein, we present the fabrication of a disposable and compact fully 3D-printed electrochemical cell incorporated into a medical scalpel enabling near-patient monitoring of surgical operations through a drop-volume voltammetric analysis, introducing the concept of the Lab-on-a-Scalpel (**Scheme 1**).

Scheme 1. Graphical illustration of the Lab-on-a-Scalpel device with the sensor and the blade attached (top). Side, front and top view of the fully 3D-printed triple electrode, along with its geometrical characteristics (bottom).

Representing a new approach, the Lab-on-a-Scalpel serves as a reliable, fast and facile sensing platform that can be produced on demand with a desktop-sized 3D printer at a very low cost (0.40 € per sensor). The combination of an essential surgical tool with an electrochemical sensor, results in a multifunctional tool which limits the number of instruments needed in the operating room. Additionally, it aims to minimize the delays during critical moments in surgery by offering real-time monitoring of the patient's biochemical profile, contributing to an overall better patient care. The sensor was investigated for the determination of epinephrine, also known as adrenaline. This hormone is crucial as it can be released in humans during stress while it also has been used from medical professionals to control bleeding, prolong anesthesia, and tackle emergency medical situations such as anaphylaxis or cardiac events.^[21,22] The electrochemical determination of epinephrine using our sensor was explored under different techniques such as cyclic voltammetry (CV), differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) and amperometry, and diverse experimental conditions (drop-volume analysis, polarization potential, stirring,

etc), aiming to fully explore its sensing capabilities across different modes of analysis. The reliability and accuracy of the sensing device were assessed separately for each of the proposed methods of analysis through recovery studies in artificial blood samples.

Results and Discussion

Printing Process

The fabrication of a fully 3D-printed electrochemical cell can sometimes be a complex procedure due to the need for the integration of two different filament materials in one structure. In particular, carbon black - polylactic acid (CB/PLA) and polylactic acid (PLA) filaments have been used interchangeably for the electrodes and insulators, respectively. The use of a dual-extruder 3D printing that will automatically change the filaments when needed is ideal for a multifilament printing procedure. Such printing model is able to reduce the fabrication time and produce ready-to-use sensing devices in a single-step printing process. Nevertheless, a dual-extruder 3D printer is an added benefit rather than a necessity. Most commercial 3D printers support multi-material printing by manual switching of filaments during the printing process, rendering the on-demand fabrication of such sensing devices highly accessible.

Geometric characteristics

The sensor was specifically designed with a shape and geometry that allows to fit and merge within a medical scalpel. It can be easily attached to the rear side, just like the blade and can be disposed of and replaced on demand (**Scheme 1 and Figure S1**). The long base facilitates the easier connection with the potentiostat and at the same time serves as a probe being able to reach inaccessible body fluids, if needed.

The thickness, the relative position, and the distance between the electrodes were selected based on basic principles of electrochemistry. In this way, the counter electrode has increased surface area that will not limit the performance of the sensor. At the same time the working electrode is located between counter and reference electrodes with their distance being the shortest possible, yet without being in contact.

The thickness of each one of the material layers determines the length of the sensing interface and thus the surface area influencing the performance of the sensor. Preliminary experiments demonstrated that thicknesses between 0.4 and 2.0 mm in sensors prevail in terms of printability and size effectiveness without any limitations in the electrochemical performance. Therefore, a 1.3 mm thickness was selected for the working electrode, and accordingly the counter electrode and reference electrode have a thickness of 1.5 and 0.48 mm, respectively (**Scheme 1**).

The electrodes were separated by a 0.5 mm insulator printed by plain PLA, allowing a close proximity between the three electrodes, thus enabling the measurement of a drop-volume solution of 50 μL . This triple electrode design constitutes a compact, simple and easy-to-prepare approach for a triple

electrode. It can serve as a promising alternative to the commercial screen-printed triple electrodes that consist of circular and arc-shaped electrodes that entail a rather complex design and production procedure.

Activation treatment

The three electrodes of the Lab-on-a-Scalpel sensing device were activated through an eco-friendly and highly reproducible electrochemical treatment by applying +1.8 V in 0.1 M PBS, without the involvement of any hazardous and toxic compound. This activation method has been extensively described in a previous study of our group^[23]; it offers enhanced sensing capabilities to the CB/PLA 3D printed electrodes providing a uniform electrochemical behavior across their surface. Such activity is enabled without deteriorating the morphology and structure of the electrode, as it exposes the carbon black over the PLA layer. In this work, all the three electrodes that constitute the fully 3D-printed sensor are electrochemically activated simultaneously, by connecting them altogether in the same crocodile clip, eliminating the need for their sequential activation.

Figure 1. Cyclic voltammograms of CB/PLA 3D printed electrodes in the presence of 1 mM of hexacyanoferrate (III) at a scan rate of 50 mV s⁻¹ using a conventional electrochemical cell where Pt foil serves as counter electrode and Ag/AgCl as reference electrode (black); CVs obtained using the fully printed electrochemical cell consisting of CB/PLA counter electrode and pseudoreference electrode (red).

Electrochemical Characterization

The electrochemical behavior of the working electrode was evaluated by monitoring the electron transfer properties of a standard redox system using a conventional three-electrode system (Ag/AgCl as the reference and Pt foil as the counter). For this purpose, 1 mM of hexacyanoferrate (III) in a 0.1 M PBS pH 7 through CV was carried out at a scan rate of 50 mV s⁻¹. Under the same experimental conditions, the suitability of CB/PLA-based counter and pseudo-reference^[24] electrode was investigated. The voltammetric profile of the fully 3D-printed electrochemical cell demonstrated in **Figure 1** illustrates an identical shape and peak

current with the conventional electrochemical cell, shifted by ca. 0.286 V towards negative potential values.

Additionally, **Figure S2** demonstrates the performance of 5 similarly prepared fully 3D-printed electrochemical cells. The stable peak current response (RSD=6.15%) ascertains the reproducible behavior of the working electrode, while the constant half wave potential $E_{1/2}$ (RSD=4.87%) confirms the suitability of the CB-PLA electrode to act as a pseudo-reference electrode.

These findings suggest that the fabrication of the fully 3D-printed electrochemical cells is a highly reproducible procedure that yields identical sensing devices that can be used autonomously without the need for any external components (i.e., counter and reference electrode). Henceforth, the fully 3D-printed electrochemical cell is utilized in further investigations.

Epinephrine electrooxidation

The sensing capabilities of the fully 3D-printed electrochemical cell have been explored with the use of epinephrine as a model analyte. It is undoubtedly one of the most important hormones to track during a surgical operation, as its abrupt concentration fluctuations are indicative of excessive stress in the body functions. Additionally, in many cases, epinephrine is injected into the patients during a surgical operation to minimize bleeding and improve the depth and duration of anesthesia. The lowest effective dose of epinephrine can improve the results of the surgery.^[22] Considering that, the accurate and instantaneous determination of epinephrine in the course of a surgical operation is of paramount importance.

Previous studies have shown that epinephrine sensing is favorable in slightly acidic conditions.^[25,26] Data demonstrated in **Figure S3** come in accordance with those studies, indicating pH 6 as an optimal condition for the determination of epinephrine. Hence, all the subsequent experiments in this research work took place in pH 6.

The electrochemical determination of epinephrine relies on its oxidation to quinone derivative. The mechanism of that reaction was revisited by Bacil et al. who proved that it follows a multi-step electron transfer with a swift intramolecular cyclization.^[27] Their findings suggests that the reaction is pH-dependent and highlight that at pH values higher than 5.21 (pK_a), the deprotonated epinephrine can undergo a cyclization after the electrochemical oxidation to the quinone derivative. Later on, the cyclic quinone derivative can be electrochemically reduced to form the cyclic epinephrine (**Figure 2A**).

In the interface of the Lab-on-a-Scalpel sensing device (**Figure 2B**), the electrochemical oxidation of the epinephrine ($E_{1(ox)}$) can be clearly identified at an onset potential of +0.2 V (vs CB/PLA), while the electrochemical reduction of the cyclic quinone derivative of epinephrine ($E_{2(red)}$) occurs at a -0.4 V (vs CB/PLA). Meanwhile the reverse electrochemical reactions that form the redox couples of those reactions (e.i. $E_{1(red)}$ to the $E_{1(ox)}$ and $E_{2(ox)}$ to the $E_{2(red)}$) are observed only in higher scan rates.

Additionally, the CVs in a wide range of scan rates revealed a linear correlation between the anodic peak current of E_1 and the square root of scan rate ($R^2=0.9939$), indicating a diffusion-controlled electrochemical process.

Figure 2. (A) Graphical illustration of epinephrine oxidation reaction following the “C”EECEE mechanism as proposed from Bacil et al.^[27] and (B) Cyclic voltammograms measured with fully 3D-printed electrochemical cell in 0.1 M PBS pH 6 containing 10 μM epinephrine, at various scan rates, along with the plot of peak current vs the scan rate and the square root of scan rate with the respective regression equations.

Modes of determination

The performance of the fully 3D-printed triple electrode for the determination of epinephrine is investigated under different experimental setups with various electrochemical techniques. **Figure 3A-C** illustrates the experimental setup, demonstrating the conditions of the experimental procedures during the analysis (whether stirring was applied and the volume of the working solution). Voltammetric analysis was carried out in 0.1 M PBS (pH 6) in the presence of varying concentrations of epinephrine and the results are demonstrated in **Figure 3A'-C'** along with the corresponding calibration plots (**Figure 3A''-C''**).

Cyclic voltammograms performed in a static working solution display a linear dependence between the anodic peak current and epinephrine over the concentration range 0.5 - 435.15 μM with the data fitting the equation $i_p (\mu\text{A}) = 0.0234[\text{Epinephrine}] (\mu\text{M}) + 0.0488$ ($R^2 = 0.9991$), while the limit of detection (LOD), calculated as $3\sigma/\text{slope}$, was found to be 0.14 μM .

Chronoamperometric technique was employed for the continuous monitoring of epinephrine. The amperometric response of fully 3D-printed electrochemical cell towards five consecutive additions of 10 μM epinephrine at various polarization potentials (**Figure S4**) reveals a favorable sensitivity emanating from +0.5 V, therefore it was selected for further exploration. **Figure 3B'** demonstrates the amperometric curve of the sensor in a stirred solution containing epinephrine over the concentration range 1 - 215.36 μM in which the sensor exhibits a linear dynamic range (**Figure 3B''**); data fit the equation $i_p (\mu\text{A}) = 0.0593[\text{Epinephrine}] (\mu\text{M}) + 0.1557$ ($R^2 = 0.9983$), with an LOD of 0.35 μM . DPV was employed for epinephrine determination through a drop-volume analysis. The sensing device was kept vertically, and 50 μL of the working solution was applied, covering the available surface area of the three electrodes (**Figure 3C**).

Figure 3. Modes of determination of epinephrine with fully 3D-printed electrochemical cell. (A-C) graphical illustration of the experimental setup of the measurement, (A'-A'') CVs in the range from 0.5 to 435.15 μM of epinephrine at a scan rate of 25 mV s^{-1} and the respective calibration plot, (B'-B'') amperometric curve at a polarization potential of $+0.5\text{ V}$ in the range from 1 to 215.36 μM of epinephrine and the respective calibration plots and (C'-C'') DP voltammograms of drop-volume analysis in the range from 0.5 to 20 μM of epinephrine and the respective calibration plots.

The performance of the electrochemical sensor is demonstrated in **Figure 3C'** where a peak in an onset potential of 0.0 V (vs CB-PLA pseudo-reference electrode) corresponds to the electrooxidation of epinephrine. The anodic peak current exhibits a linear correlation with epinephrine concentration over the range 0.5–20 μM with the data fitting the equation $i_p (\mu\text{A}) = 0.0104[\text{Epinephrine}] (\mu\text{M}) + 0.0094$ ($R^2 = 0.9927$), with an LOD of 0.43 μM .

Optimization and Performance

Aiming at enhancing the analytical performance of the sensing device, a conditioning step is introduced by agitating the working solution prior to every measurement so that the measuring species are evenly distributed and interact with the sensing surface. The magnitude of the current response in the presence of 2 μM of epinephrine along with the repeatability of the sensor for 10 consecutive measurements under different conditioning time intervals (0, 30, and 60 s) is assessed.

The repeatability of the sensor under different conditioning time intervals for 10 consecutive measurements displayed in **Figure 4A** confirms an exceptional stability of the sensor regardless of the conditioning step. The relative standard deviation (%RSD)

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was calculated as 9.70%, 0.91%, and 2.41% for 0, 30, and 60 s of conditioning, respectively. Therefore, the suitability of the sensor for conducting a full chemical analysis with a single sensor is deemed more than satisfactory.

Figure 4. Repeatability of fully 3D-printed in 0.1 M PBS pH 6 containing 2 μM epinephrine for different electroless conditioning step (0, 30, 60 s) (A) and DP voltammograms over the concentration range of 0.3–67.68 μM , recorded after 30 s conditioning step (B) with the inset displaying the respective calibration plot.

Moreover, results show that a short conditioning step such as 30 s not only improves the repeatability of the sensor but is also capable to enhance the current response, leading to a more than 3 times higher sensitivity to the epinephrine determination. These findings suggest that a short conditioning step is helpful yet not obligatory for the determination of epinephrine with the Lab-on-a-Scalpel sensing device.

The performance of the sensor under the optimal experimental conditions is evaluated using DPV. **Figure 4B** displays the DP voltammograms that were derived after a 30 s conditioning step in the presence of various concentrations of epinephrine in 0.1 M PBS (pH 6). Peak current attributed to epinephrine electrooxidation is linearly correlated with its concentration (**Figure 4B** inset) in a range of 0.3 - 67.68 μM with the data fitting the equation $i_p (\mu\text{A}) = 0.0123[\text{Epinephrine}] (\mu\text{M}) + 0.0063$ ($R^2=0.9988$). The LOD was found to be 0.13 μM .

Table 1. Comparison of reported electrochemical sensors for the determination of epinephrine with the current work.

Electrode	Technique	Conditions	Linear Range, μM	LOD, μM	Refs.
mesoporous SiO ₂ /CPE	CV	15s conditioning	1 - 60	0.6	[25]
SnO ₂ /graphen e/GCE	SWV	-	0.5 - 200	0.017	[28]
GCE/C-dots	DPV	-	0.05 - 2.0	0.0061	[29]
niacin/CPE	CV	-	20.66-174.4	0.0113	[30]
MXene/GCPE	Amperometry	At 1.2 V	0.02 - 10, 10 - 100	0.0095	[31]
Ty/MWCNTs/GCE	DPV	-	0.6 - 100	0.51	[32]
2-GMA/ITO	DPV	-	1 - 60	0.0035	[33]
Laponite clay-modified IPGE	DPV	-	0.8 - 10	0.26	[34]
G-PLA	SWV	-	4 - 80	0.23	[35]
CNF-AuNPs/GCE	SWV	-	50-1000	1.7	[26]
Lab-on-a-Scalpel (CB/PLA)	CV	-	0.5 - 435.15	0.14	This work
	Amperometry	At 0.5 V	1.0 - 215.36	0.35	
Lab-on-a-Scalpel (CB/PLA)	DPV	Drop-volume analysis	0.5 - 20.00	0.43	This work
		30s conditioning	0.3 - 67.68	0.13	

The fully 3D-printed triple electrode after a simple electrochemical activation process and without any modification offers exceptional analytical figures of merit for the determination of epinephrine, outperforming the majority of the sensors documented in the literature (**Table 1**). It allows continuous monitoring and drop-volume analysis of the target analyte, which are coveted and concurrently elusive functions in sensing devices. These features combined with the low-cost and on-demand fabrication render it a top-notch sensing device. Its ability to be incorporated into the rear side of medical scalpel along with its disposable nature highlight its uniqueness towards near-patient monitoring during a surgical operation.

Recovery Studies

The reliability and accuracy of the sensor is investigated by recovery studies in spiked artificial blood samples with known concentrations of epinephrine.

Figure 5. DP Voltammograms of non-spiked and spiked artificial blood samples in 0.1 M PBS (pH 6) along with the respective standard addition plots measured through the drop-volume analysis (A) and through immersing and conditioning the fully 3D-printed sensor (B).

The different modes of analysis were examined using the standard addition method and the results are demonstrated in i) **Figure S5** for the amperometry at +0.5 V in a 200 rpm stirring solution, ii) **Figure 5A** for the DPV through a drop-volume analysis and iii) **Figure 5B** for the DPV through immersion in a working solution after a 30 s electroless conditioning (200 rpm).

Table 2. Determination and recovery of epinephrine in artificial blood sample.

Technique	Conditions	Added, μM	Found, μM	Recovery, %
Amperometry	200 rpm continuous stirring	0	N.D.	-
		40	37.68	94.20
		80	73.70	92.12
DPV	30 s conditioning	0	N.D.	-
		20	18.26	91.31
		40	41.86	104.65
DPV	Drop- volume analysis	0	N.D.	-
		30	28.48	94.95
		60	57.22	95.37

*N.D., not detected

Recovery values ranged between 91% and 105% (**Table 2**) suggest that the sensing device is capable of operating consistently and accurately across different techniques for the determination of the analyte in artificial blood sample. These findings underscore the suitability of the sensor for broad applications in clinical diagnostics and biochemical research.

Conclusion

In this work, we successfully developed a novel, compact, and disposable fully 3D-printed electrochemical cell incorporated into the rear side of a medical scalpel, named Lab-on-a-Scalpel. It is a multifunctional tool aiming to promote the intraoperative biochemical monitoring of patients through chemical analysis, while minimizing the number of instruments required during surgery. The scalability and on-demand fabrication of the sensor along with the very low cost (0.40 € per sensor) renders the sensor a viable and practical alternative to conventional analytical methods. This device holds promise to enhance efficiency and safety of surgical procedures through immediate near-patient diagnostics. Hence, allows the healthcare professionals to take timely and more informed decisions and handle more effectively any detected abnormalities.

Lab-on-a-Scalpel was successfully applied in the electroanalytical determination of epinephrine through different electrochemical techniques showing competitive analytical figures-of-merit without the need of any modification. The high sensitivity (LOD of 130 nM), the outstanding stability (0.91% RSD of repeatability) and the exceptional accuracy (recovery of 91-105%) render Lab-on-a-scalpel a promising and reliable sensing device, that shows potential for the implementation for a wide range of biochemical analytes. Moreover, the ability to conduct full chemical analysis

with just a 50 μL drop is of high importance during a surgical procedure due to the limited availability of the sample.

All in all, Lab-on-a-Scalpel connects analytical chemistry and biomedical engineering by combining an electroanalytical sensor with a medical tool to construct an advanced multifunctional device. This device can promote point-of-care diagnostics in surgical theaters and holds promise to become an essential tool for robotic-assisted surgery. Its integration in such robotic platforms can improve the accuracy of the procedure by adjusting its actions in response to the biochemical profile of the patient.^[36] In this manner, it can improve the efficiency of the procedure and ensure patient safety. Upon connection with wireless data transmission technologies, Lab-on-a-Scalpel can communicate with other surgical instruments and monitoring systems that will pave the way for its broader adoption in next-generation smart surgical environments.

Supporting Information

The authors have cited additional references within the Supporting Information.^[14,23,37]

Data availability statement

The datasets generated and/or analyzed during the study are accessible via the Zenodo repository:
<https://zenodo.org/records/14067710>.

Acknowledgements

A. V. P. was supported by the Onassis foundation - Scholarship ID: F ZS 045-1/2022-2023 and Bodossaki foundation Scholarship. This work was supported from the grant of specific university research – grant No. A2_FCFT_2024_065. The authors would like to thank Dr. Stefanos Mourdikoudis from the University of Vigo, Spain, for fruitful discussions and technical support, and Pelagia Galani, MD, from Thriassio General Hospital of Elefsina, Greece, for insightful advice on medical matters. The authors acknowledge the assistance provided by the Advanced Multiscale Materials for Key Enabling Technologies project, supported by the Ministry of Education, Youth, and Sports of the Czech Republic. Project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004558, Co-funded by the European Union. Z.S. was supported by ERC-CZ program (project LL2101) from Ministry of Education Youth and Sports (MEYS).

Keywords: medical scalpel • 3D printing • sensing device • drop-volume voltammetric analysis • epinephrine determination

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A disposable and compact fully 3D-printed electrochemical sensor is incorporated into the rear side of a medical scalpel, leading to a multifunctional tool (Lab-on-a-Scalpel) that can facilitate near patient diagnostics in the operating theater through drop-volume analysis. This device can be an essential tool in robotic-assisted surgery and pave the way for next-generation smart surgical environments.